

Editorial

Sexual evolution during digital revolution

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The 21st century is the era of the digital revolution. Digital technology has become an integral part of daily life of most individuals. For techno people, the term 'Cloud' has a different meaning, so also the term 'Mouse'. Apple and Blackberry too have different meanings in this digital world. Digitalization has made the tasks of daily life much easier. Internet is playing a pivotal role in communication. The digital revolution brought significant changes in personal, social, professional, and recreational life. It has dramatically changed the educational and healthcare scenario. Digitalization is not limited to the developed or high-income countries. Now, the digital platform is easily available, accessible at an affordable price. As per a recent report, the highest number of internet users live in Asia though the penetration of the internet is high in Europe, North America, and Australia.

With time, people have also witnessed the adverse consequences of digitalization. Excess use of digital technology resulted in

technology addiction, which affected all ages and genders (Agarwal and Kar, 2015). Evidences support that people become victims of online sexual abuse, online bullying as well as pornography addiction (Jonsson et al., 2019; Maas et al., 2019; Wéry and Billieux, 2017).

Interestingly, sexuality is also evolved stupendously during this phase of the digital revolution. The impact of the digital revolution on sexual life can be positive or negative. Now, people can search their life-partners through various marriage portals. Digitalization facilitated dating and online friendships. The anxiety and fear encountered in interacting with the strangers and the opposite gender is minimal in the digital forums than direct contact. The beneficial effects of digitalization on sexual life are highly appreciable. At the same time, its negative impacts are also not less.

People get attracted to online sexual content, which is an easy and undaunted mode to gratify sexual appetite. Due to its instant gratifying nature, pornography is highly addictive. Pornography addiction is emerging as an important form of technology addiction in the digital era (Kar, 2016). This problematic form of cyber sex is often extreme and impairing for the individuals (Wéry and Billieux, 2017).

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Sexual violence in the form of cyber bullying, revenge porn has emerged. Many people seeking intimacy or friendship on online platforms become victims of cyberbullying and revenge porn. Several reports of crimelated to cybersex have flooded the media during recent times.

Digitalization is defining sexuality in a new fashion. It has given birth to several new psychopathologies, which have not yet received any place in the existing diagnostic systems (except Internet Gaming Disorder in DSM-5). There is a need to understand the emerging sexual-psychopathologies for prevention, diagnosis and better treatment.

References

- Agarwal, V., Kar, S.K., 2015. Technology addiction in adolescents. *J Indian Assoc Child Adolesc Ment Health* 11, 170-4.
- Jonsson, L.S., Fredlund, C., Priebe, G., Wadsby, M., Svedin, C.G., 2019. Online sexual abuse of adolescents by a perpetrator met online: a cross-sectional study. *Child Adolesc. Psychiatry Ment. Health* 13, 32.
- Kar, S., 2016. Lost Online, Then Lust Online. *J. Psychiatr. Nurs.* 5, 117-119.
- Maas, M.K., Bray, B.C., Noll, J.G., 2019. Online Sexual Experiences Predict Subsequent Sexual Health and Victimization Outcomes Among Female Adolescents: A Latent Class Analysis. *J. Youth Adolesc.* 48, 837-849.
- Wéry, A., Billieux, J., 2017. Problematic cybersex: Conceptualization, assessment, and treatment. *Addict. Behav.* 64, 238-246.